

Image Recognition of Home Objects Using Mobilenetv2 on the STM32 Embedded Platform

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Abstract—Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) are known to deliver state-of-the-art performance in image recognition tasks. However, the memory requirements and computational complexities of many CNN models make them unsuitable for resource constrained environments. Running CNN models on embedded platforms can transform user interaction with simple appliances. In this paper, dimensionality reduction and quantization was used to reduce the computing demands of MobileNetV2 architecture, making it possible to run on a STM32 microcontroller. The dimensionality multiplier was used to reduce the size of the network and quantization was used to reduce the computational complexity. The resulting network was successfully deployed on the microcontroller and recognizes objects with 87.6% accuracy in an inference time of 127ms. This study contributes to the ongoing exploration of artificial intelligence applications for resource constrained hardware.

Index Terms—Artificial intelligence, Artificial neural networks, Computer vision, Embedded systems, Object recognition

I. INTRODUCTION

In the race to improve the human computer interaction through Artificial Intelligence (AI), object recognition, a very important component of computer vision, takes prominent position. It has been established that deep learning models like Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) deliver state-of-the-art performance when applied to solve object recognition problems [1], [2], [3], [4]. However, despite their performance, most CNN models have high computational cost and are unsuitable for deployment in environments with limited memory and computational resources. This has, in recent years, yielded significant research efforts focused on implementing deep learning models, especially for object recognition tasks, on low memory, computationally limited and embedded platforms. Particular attention has been paid to reduction of memory demand and computational complexities of CNN models, leading to breakthrough state-of-the-art CNNs such as MobileNet [4]. Research in hardware implementation of vision recognition did not take a backseat either as researchers continue to explore innovative ways to bring computer vision closer to users. The work in [5] and [6] describe the implementation of a facial recognition model on a Raspberry Pi. Researchers in [7] took the work a step ahead to the visual recognition of facial expression and emotion. As an operating system (OS) based platform, the Raspberry pi is liable to latencies which are introduced by factors such as the start-up time and background processes. For applications where fast computational results are desired, it becomes imperative to consider implementing image recognition

models on microcontrollers. Microcontrollers run in real time, with no background processes and starts execution of functional code immediately on start-up. Researchers in [8], [9] and [10] used vision modules like OpenMV and Pixy for recognition tasks in their work, while limiting the STM32 microcontrollers to control functions based on the output of the vision modules. The work by [11] and [12] used template matching, which does not deliver the same state-of-the-art performance as a CNN, as the recognition algorithm deployed on the STM32 microcontrollers used in their work.

Despite that a lot of collective progress has been made on increasing the efficiency of CNNs over the last couple of decades, more work needs to be carried out to further explore reduction in computation complexity and memory demand. A key timely question pose is; are we close to efficiently running CNN models on embedded systems? In this study, we deployed a CNN model on an embedded system and investigated its performance systematically. We used quantization [13] to reduce computation cost and combined this technique with dimensionality reduction to reduce memory requirements.

In particular, we analysed the deployment of MobileNetV2 [14], a CNN model with low memory and computational requirements, on the STM32H747XI microcontroller from STMicroelectronics. The STM32 is a popular and widely used family of microcontrollers that are embedded in millions of consumer products around the world. Implementing CNN models on such a platform has tremendous potential for being incorporated in consumer electronics products and can enhance the way we interact with everyday electronic objects around us. The MobileNetV2 model is trained to recognize ten classes of home objects using TensorFlow [15] machine learning framework. The programming language used for the training is Python. The training environment used is Google Colab [16] which allows writing and execution of python code through a web browser.

This work builds on the person detection application in the FP-AI-VISION1 [17] function pack provided by STMicroelectronics. We chose the STM32H747I-DISCO board attached to a B-CAMS-OMV camera module as the deployment hardware for our model. After training our model in Colab with images in the MyNursingHome Dataset [18], we converted the model to optimized embedded C software. Then the model was combined with other components of FP-AI-VISION1 function pack and flashed onto the Cortex-M7 core of the STM32H747I-DISCO board. The deployed network is able to classify objects seen by the camera with 87.6% accuracy. The typical classification inference time is only 127 milliseconds.

In section II of this report, we describe the hardware in detail. In section III, we describe the model architecture,

training, quantization and conversion to embedded C software for deployment to the target hardware. In section IV, we discuss the results obtained from deploying the model to the hardware target and applying it for classification tasks. We draw conclusions in section V.

II. Hardware design for Recognition of Home Objects

We used the FP-AI-VISION1 function pack from STMicroelectronics as a software template for our work and the object recognition neural network model adopted for our task was MobileNetV2. The target hardware used for the deployment of the model was STM32H747I-DISCO board which has an on board thin-film-transistor (TFT) screen and the plug in camera module used for image acquisition was B-CAMS-OMV.

A. STM32H747I-DISCO

The STM32H747I-DISCO is a comprehensive development platform based on the STMicroelectronics STM32H747XIH6 microcontroller. It was designed to make the process of creating user applications with the microcontroller straightforward. The board is equipped with a 4" capacitive touch LCD display which simplifies the evaluation of our model. The STM32H747XIH6 microcontroller is a dual core microcontroller based on 32-bit Arm Cortex-M7 and 32-bit Arm Cortex-M4 cores. It has two megabytes of flash memory and 1 megabyte of RAM together with 128 Kbytes of DTCM RAM for time critical routines. With these features, clearly the STM32H747XIH6 microcontroller is a low memory resourced and computationally limited hardware.

Fig. 1. STM32H747I-DISCO

B. B-CAMS-OMV

B-CAMS-OMV is a camera module bundle for STM32 boards. It consists of a camera module adapter, STMicroelectronics camera module based on OV5640 image sensor providing 5 mega pixel resolution with 8-bit colour and a flexible flat cable.

Fig. 2. B-CAMS-OMV

C. FP-AI-VISION1

FP-AI-VISION1 [17] is a CNN based computer vision application function pack for STM32Cube. It consists of software components specifically designed for artificial intelligence-based computer vision applications, in addition to software components produced by the X-CUBE-AI Expansion Package. It employs the STM32_AI_Runtime neural networks libraries to implement an advanced computer vision application. Libraries are created using the X-CUBE-AI Expansion Package for the STM32CubeMX tool and are predicated on pre-trained models. FP-AI-VISION1 comes with a feature-rich STM32_ImageProcessing_Library, which allows for both basic and sophisticated processing operations (such as pixel colour conversion, image rescaling and face detection). Various utility functions to read and write a variety of file types are also available within the library. The function pack contains the camera and LCD drivers, together with the framework for preparing the content of the frame buffer, capturing images into it and executing the neural network inference. The function pack also contains the integration of both 32-bit floating-point and 8-bit quantized neural network models, in different memory configurations. The person detection application in the function pack, based on a CNN, makes it an attractive framework for development of our computer vision application on STM32.

III. NETWORK STRUCTURE, TRAINING AND DEPLOYMENT

A. Network structure

MobileNetV2 was chosen as the preferred architecture for our task because, like other MobileNet variants, it has been established to deliver optimal balance between performance and accuracy in low hardware resourced environments. Other supporting software, needed for successful deployment of the model, is already an implemented component of FP-AI-VISION1 package which this project builds upon. Compared to MobileNetV1, the inverted residual structure in MobileNetV2 leads to higher accuracy, without an increase in computational requirement. Although MobileNetV3 result in better performance as shown by experiments in [19] than MobileNetV2, we chose MobileNetV2 as our image classification algorithm, because the research also highlighted specifically that MobileNetV3 is tuned to mobile phone CPUs. It was established in [14] that MobileNetV2 is targeted at general low resource use cases and thus, is more suitable to our target hardware which is an embedded platform. QF-Mobile net which has been shown to eliminate the quantization loss encountered when baseline MobileNet architectures are quantized is not defined in Keras. Keras is

the leading Application Programming Interface (API) for researchers in deep learning on the TensorFlow [15] framework. Precaution was however taken to prevent quantization loss by testing inference accuracy again after quantization to ensure it still within acceptable range.

B. Training Images

The training images consist of 4000 images extracted from the MYNursingHome [18] image dataset for indoor object classification, grouped into ten classes. The extracted data was split into two categories of 2000 images each, named dataset and test-set respectively. The dataset images were used for training the network while the test-set images were used to test the post-training and post-quantization accuracies of the CNN model. Images in both categories were further grouped according to class labels. The total number of images per class is 200. Images in the classes of the dataset category were labelled with the class name, while Images in the classes folders of the test-set category were unlabelled. The naming convention adopted for all images in both categories is such that the class name is suffixed by a number representing the position of the image within the class. For example, class sofa contained images labelled sofa0001, sofa0002 and so on.

C. Training of the Network

The MobileNetV2 model was trained in Google Colab using the Python notebook provided by [20]. TensorFlow framework was used to train the network. As a prerequisite, the zipped folders of the dataset, containing images for training of the network and the test-set, containing images for testing the accuracy of the network after training, were uploaded into the Google Colab environment after which blocks of Python codes were executed in succession to pre-process the training dataset and train the model. Descriptive summaries of the tasks completed by the software during pretraining processing of the dataset and training the network are highlighted in the sections that follow.

D. Software Packages

Helpful inbuilt and third-party modules and software packages essential to the execution of input pre-processing and model training were imported. These modules and packages are; matplotlib.pyplot, numpy, tensorflow, tensorflow_datasets sklearn.metrics, seaborn, pathlib, augmenters from imgaug, Image_dataset_from_directory from tensorflow.keras.preprocessing, datasets from tensorflow.keras and randint from random.

E. Dataset and Test-set Pre-Processing

The dataset and test-set data was imported into the Python code and the randomization of the dataset through shuffling was enabled. The images were resized to 128×128 pixels and 20% of the dataset was taken for validation. The batch size was set to 16 and class labels were extracted from the data. Next, the imgaug package was used to carry out brightness, motion blur, Gaussian blur, gamma contrast, colour saturation, flip, translation and rotation transformations on the images in the training dataset to expand the dataset size. The transformed images were added as further data to the training

dataset to increase variance. Afterwards, all images in the training and validation datasets were casted to equivalent float32 representations and mapped to their respective labels.

F. Architecture and Training Parameters

The final architecture has an input layer of 128×128 with depth of 3. The next layer is a MobileNetV2 layer that is preloaded with weights that have been pre-trained on ImageNet. The width multiplier is set to 0.35, which is the least possible value due to the adopted weights. A low width multiplier reduces the number of filters, which reduces the number of features and consequently reduces the size of the network [14]. The maximum width multiplier used by the researchers is 1.4. The default fully connected layer, at the top of MobileNetV2, is not included but is instead replaced by a global average pooling layer. Then there follows a dropout layer and finally a densely connected layer with output space dimensionality equal to the number of classes and softmax activation [21]. The network has a total of 423018 parameters, occupying a total of 1.61MB of memory. Fig. 6 and Table I summarises the network. During training, a dropout of 0.1 was used to improve classification accuracy and Adam Optimization [22], with a learning rate of 0.001 was adoptedemploying stochastic gradient descent. The training of the network was done over 100 iterations of the training dataset. Each iteration was simultaneously validated with the validation dataset. The cross-entropy loss between the class labels and class predictions was calculated during each iteration and an early stopping callback finished the training, when the accuracy of the training stoped improving. After training was completed, the architecture was used to classify images in with the test-set data, to generate output predictions. The summary of the prediction results are visualized by displaying the calculated normalized confusion matrix as shown in Fig. 5. The improvement in training and validation accuracies with each epoch, is shown in Fig. 4, affirming the importance of having a high enough epoch value, to attain better training results.

Fig. 3. The Network Architecture with five layers in total.

TABLE I
NETWORK LAYERS, DEPTH, AND PARAMETERS

Network Layer Type	Depth	Number of Parameters
Input	3	0
MobileNetV2	1280	410208
Global Average Pooling	1280	0
Dropout	1280	0
Dense	10	12810

Fig. 4. Training and validation Accuracy against epoch

Fig. 5. The Confusion matrix with results for the true label for rows and the CNN predicted label for columns

G. Quantization of the Network

Quantization describes the phenomenon in which the continuous value of numerical information in the original model is approximated to lower integer representation from large floating point representation, in order to reduce the amount of calculations and mathematical complexity contained in the model [13]. Quantization makes it possible to deploy deep learning models on resource constrained and low computational capacity systems, by converting a high precision model into a low precision model, without losing the inference accuracy of the model [23]. Quantization of the trained network was achieved by converting the model into a TensorFlow Lite model. To allow post-training quantization, the optimization strategy of the conversion was set to default. The representative dataset for the quantization was generated, by creating a small subset of randomly chosen samples, from the validation dataset. The data type of the input and output layers were set to 8-bit unsigned integer down converted from the float32 representation in the original network. The TFLiteConverter.convert() method was used to generate the quantized model based on the set parameters.

H. Testing of the Quantized Model

It is important to check for loss of performance, after quantization of the model, as it is critical for any losses to be minimal, so that accuracy of the model is not jeopardized. TensorFlow Lite models cannot be run directly in Python, so an interpreter interface for running quantized models was defined. In relation to the input, shapes and memory allocations were propagated through the network. Complete details such as name, shape, data type, index, quantization parameters and sparsity parameters for the input and output tensors were obtained from the quantized model.

Finally, the quantized model was used to classify images in the testset and calculate the accuracy of the prediction which is given by the ratio of the number of correct predictions and the number of total predictions. The average accuracy on the test-set obtained after quantization was 0.876, which is acceptable and not too far off from the maximum validation accuracy obtained during training. The model was finally downloaded from the Google Colab environment for conversion into embedded C code.

I. Conversion of Trained Model to Embedded C Code

The conversion of the model to embedded C code was achieved using STM32CubeMX. This was done by creating a new project, selecting STM32H747I-DISCO as the development board, adding the X-CUBE-AI software pack for the Cortex-M7 core and loading the project. After the project was loaded into the environment, the X-CUBE-AI software pack was selected. The clock signals and the peripherals on the board were automatically configured and the generated quantized model was added as a network in X-CUBE-AI. The option to use the activation buffer for input buffer was selected. This helps to reduce memory usage, by allowing the input buffers to be reused for activations. Analysis of the model using STM32CubeMX showed that it will need 224.51KB of internal RAM, will occupy 413.13KB of internal

flash storage, consists of 70 layers and has a computational complexity of 19,106,376 multiply-adds.

The embedded C code equivalent of the model which consists of files that describe the network and its parameters was then generated.

J. Integration of Model into FP-AI-VISION1

This was done by replacing the files containing model parameters of the person detection application in FP-AI-VISION1 with the generated embedded C equivalent files, representing the trained network. The class labels of the dataset were also imported into the function pack. Finally, the application was built and deployed to the Cortex-M7 core of the microcontroller on the STM32H747I-DISCO development board.

IV. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

According to [14], the baseline MobileNet V2 architecture, used for MobileNet classification has 3.4 million parameters and performed 300 million multiply-adds. Compared to 423,018 which is the total number of parameters in our network as shown in table 1, the reduction in number of parameters is:

$$\frac{3400000 - 423018}{3400000} \times 100 = 87.6\%$$

The effect of the width multiplier in the MobileNetV2 architecture can easily be seen in the confusion matrix where for example, the network sometimes confuses refrigerators with doors. This can be attributed to the high reduction in the number of feature filters introduced by the width multiplier

As presented in [24], the memory requirement for the baseline MobileNetV2 is 14MB. The size of the network after training and quantization is 413.13KB. The percentage reduction in memory requirement is:

$$\frac{14 \times 1024 - 413.13}{14 \times 1024} \times 100 = 97.1\%$$

The percentage reduction in computing complexity can be evaluated from the multiply-adds of the base model and the dimensionally reduced and quantized model. The computational complexity reduction is:

$$\frac{300000000 - 19106376}{300000000} \times 100 = 93.6\%$$

The pre-quantization accuracy, calculated from the average of all accuracy values for class predictions after training as shown in the confusion matrix is 0.9. The post quantization accuracy obtained by using the quantized model to classify objects in the test-set is 0.876. Therefore, the drop in accuracy after quantization is:

$$\frac{0.9 - 0.876}{0.9} \times 100 = 2.4\%$$

This is a profitable trade-off for 97.1% reduction in size and 93.6% reduction in computing complexity.

In experiments in [14], using the base model on Google Pixel 1 phone to classify ImageNet resulted in a running time of 75ms. Our model was able to classify images with an inference time of 127 milliseconds as shown in Fig. 6. However, despite the high gains in memory and complexity reduction, the final application occupied a considerable amount of storage in the context of embedded systems. For example, the application occupied approximately 75% of the flash memory space available in the target hardware leaving only about 25% for other functional code. This is as a result of the drivers needed to drive the LCD and other hardware peripherals. The importance of quantization is apparent in the result, as it yielded impressive gains in reducing the computational complexity of the network to 8-bit operations without collapsing the performance of the network.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 6. Identification of home objects by the model on STM32H747I-DISCO board

V. CONCLUSION

In this study, we investigated the deployment of MobileNetV2 on the STM 32 embedded platform. We conclusively demonstrated that network size can be

significantly reduced by using a dimensionality multiplier of 0.35. Computational complexity was reduced by using quantization to generate an 8-bit representation of the network. Network training time was considerably sped up by using weights pre-trained on the ImageNet data set. Results from training and quantization of the network corroborated established conclusions that dimensionality reduction is accompanied by a reduction in feature representation and quantization is accompanied by a reduction in accuracy. The pre-quantization accuracy is 0.9 and post-quantization accuracy loss is 2.67%. Although the network is small enough to be programmed onto the flash memory of the STM32 microcontroller, combined with the other components of FP-AI-VISION1 needed to run it on the hardware, the object recognition application occupied 75% of available memory space.

Overall, the system was able to accurately recognise objects and can be easily adopted for simple, low cost computer vision applications. Further work will focus on improving feature representation within the network and improving the pre-quantization accuracy, consequently improving the post-quantization accuracy.

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